

Analytical Applications of Ion Exchange Materials. Part—IV. Selective Separation and Recovery of Thorium by Ferric Phosphate Ion Exchanger

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Manuscript received 24 December 1980, revised 5 June 1981, accepted 1 October 1981

A new method is described for the separation and recovery of Th(IV). The following mixtures have been separated: Hg(II)-Th(IV), ZrO(II)-Th(IV), Cd(II)-Th(IV), Cu(II)-Th(IV), Mn(II)-Th(IV), Zn(II)-Th(IV), Sr(II)-Th(IV) and Ni(II)-Th(IV) on ferric phosphate columns. Hg(II), ZrO(II), Cd(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Sr(II) and Ni(II) were eluted with 0.01M NH_4NO_3 and Th(IV) with a mixture of 0.01M HNO_3 + 1.0M NH_4NO_3 . Proposed studies can be applied to thorium alloys analysis.

THE analytical chemistry of thorium is complicated by the colourless nature of ions, by its simple valence state, by the lack of sufficiently selective and sensitive reagents, by the refractory nature of its ores and by its association with elements that present difficult analytical problems. In continuation of our work on analytical applications of ion exchange materials¹⁻³, it was earlier reported that Th(IV) was totally adsorbed on ferric phosphate⁴ which inspired us to study the selective separation and recovery of Th(IV) from Zr(IV) and other metal ions using ferric phosphate ion exchanger. Separation of Th(IV) from Zr(IV) has become very important in recent years because of the increasing use of zirconium metal as construction material in nuclear reactors, where even a slight impurity of thorium plays a dominant role in retarding the nuclear chain reaction to a considerable extent. Other separations achieved can be applied for the analysis of thorium in various thorium based alloys.

This paper reports the systematic studies on rapid and selective separation and recovery of Th(IV) from mixtures of cations.

Experimental

Apparatus: A glass column (i.d. 1.3 cm) was used for column operation. 1.0 g of ferric phosphate (H^+ form) was taken in the column and the flow rate was initially maintained at 1.5 ml per min.

An ELICO pH meter model LK-10 was used for pH measurements.

Reagents and Chemicals:

Ferric nitrate (BDH) and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (BDH) were used. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of ferric phosphate: Ferric phosphate was prepared by adding 0.1M aqueous solution of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate to 0.1M ferric nitrate solution as described earlier⁵. The dried product was converted into the H^+ form by treating

with 0.1M nitric acid for 24 hr with occasional shaking and intermittent changing of the acid. The product thus formed was dried at 40° in a temperature controlled oven.

Distribution coefficients: The distribution coefficients (K_d) of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Sr(II), ZrO(II) and Th(IV) were determined as usual⁶. The amounts of cations present in solution phase were estimated by EDTA (disodium salt) titrations⁶. The K_d values of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) were found to be 6.6, 15.5, 11.3, 12.5, 75.0, 9.8, 9.0 and 9.8 respectively while Th(IV) was totally adsorbed by the exchanger in water ($\text{pH} \approx 5-6$).

Elution behaviour: It was observed in preliminary elution studies that Th(IV) remained strongly adsorbed on ferric phosphate (H^+ form) bed in 0.01M NH_4NO_3 whereas Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) were completely removed through the exchanger bed. Th(IV) thus, can be eluted quantitatively with a mixture of 0.1M HNO_3 + 1.0M NH_4NO_3 (1 : 1) solution.

Procedure: The ion exchanger column (H^+ form) was washed with demineralized water before passing the test solution. A known volume of test solution (or synthetic mixture) was taken and was recycled thrice through the exchanger bed at the flow rate of 1.5 ml per min. The column was then washed with 0.01M NH_4NO_3 . Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) percolated out with the effluent and washing liquid. The adsorbed Th(IV) was then eluted quantitatively with a mixture of 0.1M HNO_3 + 1.0M NH_4NO_3 (1 : 1) solution.

Results and Discussion

It is obvious from the results that the K_d values of Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) are much less than Th(IV).

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF Th(IV) FROM SOLUTIONS CONTAINING 5,000 µg EACH OF Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Sr(II) AND ZrO(II)

Recovery of	Eluents	Volume of effluent (ml)	Amount of Th(IV)		Error %
			Loaded (µg)	Recovered (µg)	
Th(IV) from impurities	0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	50	—	—	
Th(IV) from impurities	0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	10	1,000	1,000	0.0
Th(IV) from impurities	0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	60	—	—	
Th(IV) from impurities	0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	35	10,000	10,000	0.0

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Th(IV) FROM SOLUTIONS CONTAINING Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) AND ZrO(II) ON FERRIC PHOSPHATE (H⁺ FORM) COLUMNS

Separation	Eluent	Vol. of effluent (ml)	Amount of cation			N ^a	h ^b
			loaded (µg)	Recovered (µg)	Error %		
Cu(II)-Th(IV)	Cu(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	35	5883	5851	-0.54	6.3	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Ni(II)-Th(IV)	Ni(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	20	2348	2348	0.0	6.55	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Zn(II)-Th(IV)	Zn(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	5393	5393	0.0	6.60	0.197
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Cd(II)-Th(IV)	Cd(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	25	4720	4777	+1.1	6.43	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Hg(II)-Th(IV)	Hg(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	25	10932	10932	0.0	6.90	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Mn(II)-Th(IV)	Mn(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	1705	1705	0.0	6.43	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
Sr(II)-Th(IV)	Sr(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	25	4381	4381	0.0	6.43	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		
ZrO(II)-Th(IV)	ZrO(II)-0.01 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	25	2144	2144	0.0	6.43	0.788
	Th(IV)-0.1 M-HNO ₃ +1.0 M-NH ₄ NO ₃	30	6380	6310	-1.1		

a=Minimum number of theoretical plates.
b=Height equivalent to one theoretical plate.

Hence Th(IV) can be separated from these metal ions.

Recovery of Th(IV) : Table 1 shows the successful recoveries of Th(IV) from solutions containing Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II). In the presence of a five fold excess of these metal ions, all of them could be eluted with 0.01 M NH₄NO₃ leaving Th(IV) on the column. The retained Th(IV) was easily eluted with a mixture of 0.1 M HNO₃+1.0 M NH₄NO₃ (1 : 1) solution. This demonstrates the importance of ferric phosphate in the recovery of Th(IV).

Column separations : Unlike Th(IV), which was retained by the exchanger, Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) passed out unadsorbed. Quantitative separation of these metal ions from Th(IV) has been successfully achieved. Table 2 shows a list of separations successfully achieved on a column of ferric phosphate. The order and the eluents are presented in Figs. 1-8.

The minimum number of theoretical plates (N), necessary for separation as tabulated in Table 2, were calculated using the equation⁷,

$$N \geq 2\pi \left[\frac{\frac{K_{d,Th} + a}{K_{d,M} + a} + 1}{\frac{K_{d,Th} + a}{K_{d,M} + a} - 1} \right]^2$$

Fig. 1. Separation of Cu²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

where K_{d,Th} and K_{d,M} are distribution coefficients of thorium and the metal ion separated respectively and a is the Void fraction (~0.4). The values of height equivalent to one theoretical plate (h), as reported in Table 2, can be determined from the data obtained from an elution curve

$$h = \frac{Lb^2}{8v_{max}^2}$$

Fig. 2. Separation of Ni²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 5. Separation of Hg²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 3. Separation of Zn²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 6. Separation of Mn²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 4. Separation of Cd²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 7. Separation of Sr²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

Fig. 8. Separation of ZrO²⁺ from Th⁴⁺.

where L is the length of the ion exchange column (cm), v_{\max} is the eluent volume at peak (ml) and b is the peak width (ml) at a height of $0.368 C_{\max}$. The values of N and h are given in Table 2. The h values for all the separations except Zn(II)-Th(IV) is 0.788 because the elution behaviour of Zn(II) is different from other ions i.e. $v_{\max} = 10$ ml for Zn(II) as compared to $v_{\max} = 5$ ml for Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Sr(II) and ZrO(II) as shown in Figs. 1-8. The value of h for Zn(II) is 0.197.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor Harjit Singh for facilities. One of them (H. S.) is also thankful to U. G. C. for financial assistance.

References

1. J. P. RAWAT and P. S. THIND, *Acta Ciencia India*, 1977 **3**, 120.
2. P. S. THIND and S. S. SANDHU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 260.
3. P. S. THIND, Unpublished work.
4. P. S. THIND and H. SINGH, Unpublished work.
5. J. P. RAWAT and P. S. THIND, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1976, **54**, 1892.
6. C. N. REILLY, R. W. SCHMID and F. S. SADEK, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1956, **36**, 555.
7. J. INCZEEDY, "Analytical Applications of Complex Equilibria", John Willey and Sons. Inc., New York, 1976, p. 278.